

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Introduction

At this first moment of contact, the interviewer is introduced, as well as explaining how the interview will take place, its objectives and ethical precautions

Hello, my name is Thalia, I am a master's student in the Postgraduate Program in Computer Science at the Institute of Informatics of the Federal University of Goiás. I'm carrying out my master's research on the teaching of Requirements Engineering in the context of Specification and Validation, which I'm developing into an educational strategy for adoption in higher education courses in Computing, especially within the disciplines linked to Software Requirements.

You were invited to take part in this interview because of your collaboration with this study, having taught a course considering this approach. First of all, I would like to thank you for adopting this teaching strategy in your classes and for agreeing to take part in this interview. The aim is to obtain information about your perceptions during this process so that we can carry out an evaluation of the teaching strategy employed. It's important to note that this evaluation only involves the part of the lessons that include specification and validation activities.

I would like to ask for your consent to record this interview. I reiterate that the information will only be used for research purposes, which will then be transcribed, and the data analyzed will be presented in the text of my dissertation and scientific articles, with the answers duly anonymized in order to guarantee all the necessary ethical care.

Therefore, do you authorize the recording?

And do you agree to continue with the interview?

To begin with, if you think it will make our conversation easier, you can access the Trello board used in your course, which brings together various artifacts present in the lessons taught. So, if you have any questions and want to remember how something happened, feel free to consult it.

Characterization questions

Questions are asked to break the ice for the interview to begin, collecting objective data

1. How many years have you been teaching Requirements Engineering (RE)? Or even in related areas?
2. In addition to this experience as a teacher, do you also have experience in areas such as research and/or the ER market?
 - 2.1. If so, how many years?

3. Which course did you teach that involved the teaching strategy being evaluated?
4. What was the name of the course?
5. Which semester was the course offered?
6. And in which teaching modality: face-to-face, remote or hybrid?

Thematic Blocks

After establishing trust between the parties, we arrived at the core of the interview, subdivided into thematic blocks

Organizational aspects

7. With regard to lesson planning, how do you see it in relation to the requirements specification lessons?
8. And now about the validation classes, what was your perception of the planning of the classes?
9. How do you see the organization of time for the specification and validation classes?
 - 9.1. Are there any differences you'd like to comment on?
10. Regarding the organization of the space, how would you rate the use of the computer lab for the classes?
11. Regarding the participation of the various actors involved in the teaching strategy: students, monitors and even you as a teacher. What was your perception of each person's role?
12. And for the teaching modality in which the subject was taught, how do you see the adequacy of the organization of the classes?

Content aspects

13. In this teaching strategy that you applied, various materials were developed: from slides, lesson plans, cards with information that were kept in Trello, and even the creation and structuring of the boards themselves in the tool. So, how would you rate the collaboration of the teaching materials in carrying out the requirements specification and validation classes?
14. Now, with regard to the activities that were carried out between the groups of students, how do you see these activities working for the progress of the lessons?

Methodological aspects

15. Can you tell us how the student evaluations were carried out?
16. How do you think the forms of interaction and communication used in this approach may have influenced the teaching and learning of software requirements?
17. Is there anything you would change about the assessment procedures adopted?
 - 17.1. If so, what?

Technological aspects

18. How would you rate your experience of using the Trello tool for requirements specification activities?
19. And for validation activities, how would you rate your experience with Trello?
20. Regarding the resources offered by the Trello tool, such as boards, labels, activity history, checklists, among others, how do you perceive the adequacy of these resources in relation to the needs of the teaching strategy?
21. As for the tool, did you miss anything that would improve the teaching strategy?

Soft Skills

In addition to everything we've already discussed, a point that also needs to be considered is the issue of soft skills. Soft skills are skills linked to human behavior, which have been considered of equal relevance and prominence to hard skills (technical skills) and which have also been considered within this teaching strategy. Examples include teamwork, critical thinking, communication, etc.

22. Do you believe that soft skills were developed in the students through the way the specification and validation lessons were conducted?
 - 22.1. If so, could you cite examples?
23. Given your experience in RE, do you see any relationship between the development of soft skills and the proper exercise of the profession of requirements engineer?

Closing

Closing questions, leading to a slowdown in the conversation

24. How do you compare your previous experiences of teaching requirements (before using this teaching strategy) and now, having used this approach?
25. In your opinion, what was the biggest challenge in adopting this strategy in the classroom during the course?
26. Is there anything you think needs to be changed in the teaching strategy?
 - 26.1. If so, what?
27. Would you recommend using the strategy to other teachers? Why?

Final considerations

Final moments for free comments and questions

28. Is there anything you'd like to comment on that wasn't said during the interview?